

The Influence of Quality of E-Wom, Perceived Information Usefulness, Needs of Information on Purchase Intention of Online Shop MSME Consumers through Social Media Usage as Mediation

Tanti Stevany Andriani, Erna Sofriana Imaningsih, Dudi Permana, Mas Wahyu Wibowo
Master of Management, Department of Economy and Business,
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The occurrence of the Covid-19 pandemic has had an impact on changes in consumer behavior. There has been a shift in the marketplace from offline to online, consumers no longer make the purchase process directly, but use digital platforms, namely through online shopping. However, there are often doubts and risk factors for the product to be purchased, which can hinder the next purchase process. Therefore companies need to think about a marketing strategy to minimize this risk by involving the role of social media which is an important means of communication in the post-pandemic era. Reviews given by other consumers will be useful for other potential customers, as well as information regarding products purchased and product quality based on reviews from other consumers. Online reviews on social media will be able to increase the intention of potential consumers, especially for MSME products that are still unknown to the wider community and have low sales growth. Based on this phenomenon and previous research related to consumer intention, this study aims to examine and analyze the effect of usability, information needs, and quality of online reviews on consumer intentions through the role of social media on MSME products in the Post-Pandemic period. The research population is all generations of e-commerce in Indonesia. The sampling technique was carried out using a purposive sampling technique and the analytical method uses a Partial Least Square based Structural Equation Model.

Keywords:- Quality of E-Wom; Information Usefulness; Needs of Information; Social Media Usage; Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The growth of internet users in the world has increased consistently from year to year. Around the world. The ease of getting internet access coupled with the lifestyle of modern humans who demand speed, the increase in internet users has occurred not only in developed countries, but also in all countries including Indonesia. In the midst of an increase in internet users, the world suddenly entered a phase of life that changed various behaviors, due to the spread of the covid 19 virus. The disease spread very quickly throughout the world which caused a pandemic where everyone in the world was forced to stay at home and not allowed to leave the house to prevent the spread of covid

getting wider except in important conditions. Most crowded places and markets are closed during the pandemic, forcing consumers to meet their shopping needs indirectly. In the last few years until 2022 there has been an increase in internet users, especially during the pandemic on a global scale.

Indonesia as one of the countries with the largest population of internet users in the world has also experienced an increase. Based on the following data, it appears that internet users in Indonesia have increased significantly during the pandemic. This increase is also suspected to be due to changes in people's shopping patterns, from offline to online shopping, where digital platforms and social media play an important role in this change. People no longer shop in person, but move to a new marketplace, namely online shopping. The convenience of an online-based business attracts a number of people to try shopping online. This change in behavior is very interesting, because in the midst of drastic growth, there is a group of consumers who are actually hesitant to shop online, especially for products that are not yet well-known and are produced by MSMEs. In Indonesia there are 160 million active users of social media (Haryanto, 2020).

However, even though online-based businesses are growing with a significant number of social media users, consumers are often unsure about the products offered, doubtful about the uncertainties of the products or services offered, such as payment security, fraud and product quality that does not meet expectations. The emergence of consumer awareness of risk can influence purchase intention or purchase intention. In this case, the function of social media has also developed. Social media has turned into a place where information can be collected and provided to consumers. With online social media to discuss and share information about products and services, especially through Electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM).

MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) have contributed to Indonesia's GDP by 61.07 percent or Rp. 8,573.89 trillion. The contribution of MSMEs that have an impact on the Indonesian Economy can absorb 97 percent of the total workforce and have accumulated up to 60.4 percent of the total available investment (BEKRAF, 2020). This research wants to raise one of the online shop SMEs, The Special Treats, which is engaged in the pastry shop business. Special Treats cake shop utilizes online reviews as a form of

product promotion on social media. Online review is a part of electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM), where it plays an important role as a medium for communicating digitally. Through E-WOM, information related to products or services is disseminated to all internet users, especially those who are members of social media. E-WOM contains messages or consumer reviews regarding the experience of consuming a product. The information submitted can be in the form of product quality reviews or services by the seller, provided by consumers regarding product purchasing experience, and can be used as a medium for delivering information regarding product quality and seller services (Damayanti, 2019). One and the same product is very likely to get different online reviews from consumers. Therefore information through e-WOM is important to note as a marketing strategy in shaping consumer behavior (Filiari, 2015).

Online reviews or e-wom are generally used by consumers to obtain product information based on the experiences of various consumers who have enjoyed their services and products, both in terms of the positive and negative sides regarding the quality of the products received, the packaging of goods to the speed or accuracy of delivery of goods which can affect the buying interest of consumers who reads.

Previous research has shown that purchase intention is influenced by e-WOM, Usefulness and adoption which have been dominated by the variables Perceived informativeness,

Perceived Persuasiveness, Source Expertise, Source Trustworthiness towards e-WOM Usefulness (Duong et al, 2019). In addition, other findings also show the factors of Involvement, Sense of Belonging, Trust, Tie Strength, Informational Influence have a significant positive effect on Online Purchase Intentions with mediation of e-W intention. Meanwhile Social Media Usage was found as a moderating variable that can increase the effect of e-Wom intention on Purchase Intention (Bilal et al., 2021). Social Media is an important factor because it helps social media members get information through reviews. However, previous research that raised Social Media usage as a mediating variable that can increase purchase intention has not been explored much.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Information Acceptance Model (IACM)

The Information Acceptance Model (IACM) is a theory developed by Erkan and Evans (2016) from the Information Adoption Model (IAM). This theory was developed from the Information Adoption Model which integrates Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). The combination of TRA and IAM forms IACM which can represent consumer behavior regarding E-WOM information and can expand the concept of receiving information and explain the process of influencing behavioral intentions. IACM is more in-depth about consumers adopting e-WOM information than developing purchase intentions. (Erkan and Evans 2016 in Leong, Loi and Woon 2021).

I. Erkan, C. Evans / Computers in Human Behavior 61 (2016) 47–55

Image 1: Information Acceptance Model (IACM)

B. Quality of e-WOM

The quality of e-WOM is the quality of a content from consumer reviews. e-WOM is a forum for sharing information about reviews that can assist consumers in making it a benchmark for goods or services. The e-WOM theory of Cheung and Thadani (2012) is clarified by Ho (2020) that e-WOM is consumers exchanging information about products and businesses online or online. The quality of e-WOM can also be interpreted as the quality in consumer reviews that can determine consumer buying interest. In a literal sense, e-WOM and WOM have some similarities and differences even though the electric Word of Mouth is still a derivative of Word of Mouth and is growing rapidly every

year due to technological advances that are increasingly practical.

C. Perceived Information Usefulness

Beiley and Pearson (1983) in Ho (2020) stated that Perceived Information Usefulness aims at up-to-date and informative information which can provide insight into a perception of people or consumers in increasing the effectiveness of the information obtained. This makes consumers or people who get information will test directly or indirectly to measure the usefulness of the information obtained and how much influence the information obtained influences people's perceptions. Erkan and Evans (2016) in Ho (2020) revealed that previous research found the use of

social media that is involved in large numbers can affect greater purchase intention and if the information obtained is useful.

D. Needs of Information

According to Flynn et al. (1996) in Sadar and Ali (2020) states that humans who are curious in seeking information generally have a need to collect as much information as possible, especially in gathering buying interest. The validity of the questions that are formed in gathering information according to Kelley in Sadar and Ali (2020) is consensus, characteristics and confirmation of information from sources that demand recommendations from sources of information that must always be the same.

E. e-WOM Adoption in Social Media Usage

Technological advances are increasingly rapidly making Word of Mouth can be found anywhere, including electronic Word of Mouth. One of them is through social media covid19 which can provide various illustrations and different demographics. Meyers (2017) in Bilal et al. (2021) explains that social media in its daily use can provide complete information and this is an important source of information for consumers and online communities. Because of this, the target marketers and consumer segments become more

G. Framework

Image 2: Framework

H. Hypothesis:

- H1: Quality of eWom has a positive and significant relationship with eWom adoption of special treats pastries.
- H2: Information usefulness has a positive and significant relationship with ewom adoption of special treats pastries.
- H3: Needs of Information has a positive and significant effect on eWom Adoption of special treats pastries.
- H4: e-WOM Adoption mediates the effect of e-WOM's predictor on consumer buying interest in special treats pastries.
- H5: Quality of e-WOM has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchase intentions for special treats pastries.

- H6: Information usefulness has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention of special treats pastry products.
- H7: Needs of Information has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchase intentions for special treats pastries.
- H8: e-WOM Adoption mediates Quality of eWom and Purchase intention
- H9: e-WOM adoption mediates Needs of Information and Purchase Intention
- H10: e-WOM adoption mediates Information Usefulness and Purchase Intention

III. METHODS

In this study, quantitative research was used includes a survey method research method in order to determine the

effect of e-WOM such as Quality of e-WOM (X1), Information Usefulness (X2) and Needs of Information (X3) with Social Media Usage (Y) as mediator on purchasing intentions (Z) with e-WOM adoption at The Special Treats pastry shop. The data to be obtained uses a structured quantitative data method based on a Likert scale of 1-5 from Strongly Disagree (STS) to Strongly Agree (SS). The type of sample used is purposive sampling which is limited to people who are specific enough to be able to provide the information needed because they have defined information criteria. In distributing this questionnaire, to obtain data, the questionnaire/survey was distributed online using the Google form to respondents up to 105 respondents who had visited the Instagram and Facebook pages of The Special Treats online store before filling in the questionnaire for 2 to 3 weeks to process the data.

In analyzing the data, this study using Partial Least Squares (PLS) based on the SmartPLS 3.2.8 software from structural equation modeling (SEM) for data processing.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

A. Testing Measurement model's outer model

The model specification stage relates to the Inner Model as well as the Outer Model. The Inner Model is a structural model that shows the relationship between the constructs that have been evaluated. Meanwhile, Outer Models can be referred to as measurement models used in assessing the relationship between indicator variables and suitable constructs. Outer models includes outer loading, cross loading factor, discriminant validity and fornell-larcker criterion.

Image 3: Factor Loading

Convergent Validity results are determined by Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The AVE value used is ≥ 0.5 , but this is different from the recommendations for AVE

values which are above 0.7. For Cronbach's alpha, it has the conditions above 0.7. Following are the results of data processing for Outer Loading using SmartPLS 3.0:

Table 1: Outer Loading

	IU	NOI	PI	QOE	SMU (EA)
SMU1	0.688	0.571	0.55	0.6	0.77
SMU2	0.704	0.659	0.596	0.67	0.846
SMU3	0.614	0.558	0.597	0.543	0.846
SMU4	0.66	0.549	0.571	0.528	0.808
IU1	0.883	0.581	0.563	0.744	0.747
IU2	0.824	0.646	0.513	0.594	0.675
IU3	0.797	0.545	0.468	0.556	0.614
NOI2	0.588	0.763	0.377	0.526	0.562
NOI3	0.539	0.828	0.447	0.551	0.601
NOI4	0.566	0.796	0.406	0.523	0.547
PI1	0.603	0.441	0.871	0.563	0.654
PI2	0.448	0.363	0.837	0.498	0.585
PI3	0.536	0.474	0.872	0.496	0.619
PI4	0.526	0.493	0.848	0.524	0.563
QOE1	0.642	0.567	0.51	0.805	0.611
QOE2	0.605	0.601	0.449	0.835	0.604
QOE3	0.622	0.484	0.51	0.782	0.585
QOE5	0.472	0.407	0.408	0.668	0.394

According to Table 1, all the constructs and indicators of each variable have a value or higher correlation level compared to the other variable indicators when juxtaposed.

Table 2: Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Syarat (> 0,5)
IU	0.697	Pass
NOI	0.634	Pass
PI	0.735	Pass
QOE	0.601	Pass
SMU (EA)	0.669	Pass

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) results show that the average variable has a result above 0.5 and the result of the purchase intention variable has a result of 0.753 which

can be said to have very satisfactory results or meet the recommendation requirements.

Table 3: Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Recommendation	Information
	QOE1	0.805	> 0,7	Valid
	QOE2	0.835	> 0,7	Valid
	QOE3	0.782	> 0,7	Valid
	QOE5	0.668	> 0,7	Fail
	IU1	0.883	> 0,7	Valid
	IU2	0.824	> 0,7	Valid
	IU3	0.797	> 0,7	Valid
	NOI2	0.763	> 0,7	Valid
	NOI3	0.828	> 0,7	Valid
	NOI4	0.796	> 0,7	Valid
	SMU1	0.770	> 0,7	Valid
	SMU2	0.846	> 0,7	Valid
	SMU3	0.846	> 0,7	Valid
	SMU4	0.808	> 0,7	Valid
	PI1	0.871	> 0,7	Valid
	PI2	0.837	> 0,7	Valid
	PI3	0.872	> 0,7	Valid
	PI4	0.848	> 0,7	Valid

Based on the results, all variable indicators have an Outer Loading value that is greater than 0.7 which shows a high inter-indicator relationship to each variable. The QOE5 indicator has a number below 0.7 or has a number below the recommendation requirements. However, basically this value can be said to pass because the value is above 0.50. In

the data processing test above, three indicators; QOE4, IU4, NOI1 were not included in the data processing because they affected the results of Fornell-Larcker and Discriminant Validity which could not meet the requirements. The following data processing is based on the Fornell Larcker Criterion:

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	IU	NOI	PI	QOE	SMU (EA)
IU	0.835				
NOI	0.707	0.796			
PI	0.619	0.516	0.857		
QOE	0.762	0.670	0.608	0.775	
SMU (EA)	0.816	0.717	0.708	0.718	0.818

The results of the data processing above show that all variables and indicators have a higher value than when juxtaposed with different indicators and variables where the variable indicator values are made specifically for these indicators. It can be concluded that Needs of Information for Perceived Information Usefulness, Quality of e-WOM for Perceived Information Usefulness, Quality of e-WOM for Needs of Information, and Social Media Usage for Perceived Information Usefulness and Social Media Usage for Needs of Information have a value above the terms/conditions which can be interpreted that it has no correlation or has passive correlation.

B. Testing Measurement model's Construct Reliability and Validity

The results of construct reliability and validity were evaluated through internal consistency, namely the composite results of reliability and Cronbach's alpha. Composite Reliability is an alternative in the Convergent Validity test with a reflective measurement model. The results of data processing with 0.60-0.70 are acceptable for exploratory research. However, if the value is between 0.70 - 0.90 then it can be categorized as a satisfactory result of the data value. For Cronbach's alpha it functions as an indicator in construct variables that produce reliable or reliable validity. Cronbach's alpha results > 0.70 can be categorized

as a condition on the scale. The following is the result of data processing for Composite Reliability and Cronbach

alpha as follows:

Table 5: Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
IU	0.783	0.792	0.873	0.697
NOI	0.711	0.714	0.838	0.634
PI	0.880	0.882	0.917	0.735
QOE	0.777	0.791	0.857	0.601
SMU (EA)	0.835	0.836	0.890	0.669

It can be seen that each of the variables has a Cronbach's alpha value above a scale of 0.70 which can be interpreted as an indicator of the variable being tested that can produce reliable validity. Meanwhile, the Composite Reliability results have a value of between 0.80-0.90 which can be concluded that almost all variables can be said to be satisfactorily reliable. However, the Purchase Intention variable in Composite Reliability has a value above 0.90 which can be interpreted as a very satisfactory result.

C. Testing Measurement model's Inner Model

In the Inner Model Evaluation results, there are several ways to evaluate the structural model to find out the results of hypothesis testing namely; Coefficient of Determination, Effect Size, Cross-Validated Redundancy, Path Coefficients and Significance.

Table 6: R Square

	R Square
PI	0.523
SMU (EA)	0.715

Other variables are moderately related to Purchase Intention which has a value of 0.523 and is included in the moderate or moderate influence category. However, the R square value on the variable on Social Media Usage (EA)

has a value of 0.715 which indicates that it is included in the medium-strong influence category. The value of Social Media Usage shows that Perceived Information Usefulness, Quality of e-WOM and Needs of Information represent 71.5% by the characteristics of Social Media Usage in that model.

Table 7: F Square

	PI	SMU (EA)
IU	0.001	0.344
NOI	0.003	0.092
QOE	0.036	0.032
SMU (EA)	0.194	

The results of the data processing above show that Perceived Information Usefulness and Needs of Information have no influence on Purchase Intention with values of 0.001 and 0.003. Meanwhile, the Quality of e-WOM shows a good effect in a small form on Purchase Intention. Social media Usage (EA) has a good effect on a moderate scale on purchase intention. Furthermore, the results of Needs of Information and Quality of e-WOM have a good effect on a small scale on Social Media Usage with a value of 0.092 and 0.032, while Perceived Information Usefulness has a good effect on a large scale on Social Media Usage (EA), 0.344.

Table 8: Q Square

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
IU	315.000	315.000	
NOI	315.000	315.000	
PI	420.000	266.442	0.366
QOE	420.000	420.000	
SMU (EA)	420.000	230.168	0.452

The Table 8 shows that Purchase Intention and Social Media Usage (EA) have a strong predictive relationship to

the model that has been formed with an SMU (EA) value of 0.452 and PI 0.366.

Table 9: Hypothesis Test

No	Hypothesis	β value	t value	Result	P values
H1	Quality of e-WOM -> Social Media Usage	0.154	0.167	Rejected	0.086
H2	Perceived Information Usefulness -> Social Media Usage	0.530	5.993	Accepted	0.000
H3	Needs of Information -> Social Media Usage	0.239	2.176	Accepted	0.007
H4	Social Media Usage -> Purchase Intention	0.570	3.501	Accepted	0.096
H5	Quality of e-WOM -> Purchase Intention	0.213	2.036	Accepted	0.042
H6	Perceived Information Usefulness-> Purchase Intention	0.032	0.227	Rejected	0.821
H7	Needs of Information -> Purchase Intention	-0.058	0.497	Rejected	0.619
H8	Quality of e-WOM -> Social Media Usage -> Purchase Intention	0.088	1.558	Rejected	0.120
H9	Needs of Information -> Social Media Usage -> Purchase Intention	0.136	2.003	Accepted	0.046
H10	Perceived Information Usefulness -> Social Media Usage -> Purchase Intention	0.302	2.939	Accepted	0.003

Based on the results of the data processing above, it shows that six of the ten hypotheses are accepted, namely H2, H3, H4, H5, H9 and H10. And H1, H6, H7, H8 have rejected results. This is because H2, H3, H4, H5, H9 and H10 have independent variables, each of which has a positive and significant influence on the dependent variable. While H1, H6 and H8 have positive and insignificant influence on the dependent variable. However, H7 has a negative and insignificant effect on the dependent variable.

D. Discussion

Based on the results of the data that has been processed using SmartPLS3.0, the Quality of e-WOM (X1) variable for the research model is found that the Quality of e-WOM variable has a positive but not significant effect on Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) (H1). This is contrary to Ho et al. (2021) who found that the quality of online reviews has a positive and significant effect on e-WOM adoption which explains that the quality of e-WOM can confirm product quality and product popularity. The quality of online reviews about The Special Treats stores and products affects social media users but not significantly which can be interpreted as only having enough influence for social media users who wants to buy but not entirely that online reviews can be adopted according to the user's use of social media.

Perceived Information Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Social Media Usage (H2). This is supported by research conducted by Cheung in Dachyar and Banjarahor (2017) which shows that Perceived Information Usefulness has a positive and significant effect. In addition, the research model conducted by Leong, Loi and Woon (2022) also shows that the use of information helps in increasing buying interest in online shopping where the use of information is crucial in exchanging thoughts from reviews or comments. It was found that the information obtained from online reviews about The Special Treats stores and products is very easy to be adopted by users or consumers in using social media which can help consumers in forming a perception.

Needs of Information has a positive and significant relationship to Social Media Usage (H3). In research Sardar et al (2021) found that consumers perceive NOI as a significant factor in their decision to adopt online reviews. Torres et al (2018) also found NOI to have a significant relationship. Noi can inform that consumers search for information through social media and have perceptions about the information adopted. Information needs are very influential in adopting online or e-WOM reviews of The Special Treats stores and products on social media towards their users. This shows that social media users or potential consumers need more information through online reviews to be adopted as the use of social media in determining their perceptions.

The results of data processing found to show that Social Media Usage has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention (H4). Research by Sardar et al. (2021) stated that Social Media Usage or e-WOM adoption helps in making purchase recommendations into actual purchases. Adoption of e-WOM and use of social media play an important role in creating the impact of reviews on consumer purchase intentions. Leong, Loid an Woon (2022) and Rahaman et al (2022) found that e-WOM adoption has a significant positive relationship to consumer buying interest. Based on the results of the data processing above, it was found that the use of social media and adopting online reviews can generate buying interest. Where social media users who see and accommodate or adopt online reviews about The Special Treats store and products have the potential to generate interest in buying interest.

In this study found that the Quality of e-WOM has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention (H5). This is supported by research from Fan et dal in Ho Khanh and Duy (2020) which states that the quality of e-WOM has a positive and significant relationship to consumer buying interest. The quality of online reviews can affect whether or not buying interest appears. The better the quality of the reviews that both the store and The Special Treats products have, the more it can increase consumer

buying interest. The majority of respondents agreed that the quality of online reviews of The Special Treats stores and products represents their opinion.

Perceived Information Usefulness has a positive but insignificant effect on Purchase Intention (H6). Research on Moslehpour et. al (2018) and Entre and Kolbe (2020) make Perceived Information Usefulness a significant predictor. Erkan and Evans (2016) in Rahaman et al (2022) suggest that online purchasing of information is driven by the extent to which information can be considered valuable. The results are not significant on the perceived usefulness of Perceived Information on Purchase Intention indicating that consumers who have received information depend on how useful the information obtained is or not for consumers. However, the use of this information does not necessarily make consumers interested or generate an interest in buying the shop and products from The Special Treats. The influence of Perceived Information Usefulness is not significantly determined by the good or bad use of the information that consumers get. If consumers feel that the review information is not clear about what they are looking for from the store and products from The Special Treats, then it is not certain that consumers will be interested or have an interest in making a purchase.

Needs of Information has a negative and insignificant effect on Purchase Intention (H7). This contradicts previous research showing that Ali (2021) found Needs of Information to play a very important role with online Purchase Intention. Gupta et al, (2021) stated that Needs of Information can provide information that consumers are looking for social media information to be more useful. This shows that the higher the level of information need (NOI) for consumers or social media users, the lower the consumer's buying interest (PI). However, because it is not so significant, information needs cannot determine one's buying interest. In this study, information needs cannot be used as a benchmark for consumers to generate buying interest. The majority of respondents have the perception that the need for information about The Special Treats stores and products does not affect their buying interest. This is due to the possibility that the need for information about The Special Treats shop and products is high, but due to the lack of informative online reviews that are obtained, it makes consumers tend not to buy/cannot determine their buying interest.

Data processing on the e-WOM adoption hypothesis mediating Quality of e-WOM and Purchase Intention (H8) shows that this hypothesis has a positive effect but not significant. This is supported but differs from previous research from Erkan and Evans in Leong, Loid and Woon (2001) who found that information through e-WOM can be easily adopted by consumers to form buying interest and the quality of information or e-WOM is a matter of concern. The results from the respondents of this study indicate that the quality of online reviews of The Special Treats stores and products that have been considered or adopted by consumers through the use of social media in seeking information may or may not raise consumer buying interest. However, the quality of the resulting online reviews does not

fully represent or support consumer opinion where when considered and adopted by the use of social media it is not necessarily the emergence of significant consumer buying interest.

In this study it was found that the Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) hypothesis is positive and significant when mediating Needs of Information and Purchase Intention (H9). In previous research based on Leong, Loid an Woon (2021) states that the needs of information adopted has a correlation with Purchase Intention. Gupta, et. al (2020) also found that consumers who adopt information based on information needs can inform consumers so that buying interest arises. In this study, the more information about The Special Treats shops and products that is informative and can meet the information needs sought by consumers through the use of social media in the process of adopting online reviews, the more interest in buying from consumers will arise.

The results of the hypothesis data shows that e-WOM adoption has a positive and significant influence mediating Perceived Information Usefulness and Purchase Intention. Previous research conducted by Erkan and Evans in Leong, Loi and Woon (2021) found that the usefulness of information is used as a predictor in the adoption of online reviews and purchase intention. Dachyar and Banjarnahor (2017) found a positive and significant correlation between information adoption, information usefulness and consumer buying interest. With the use of social media, it can provide informative and useful information for adoption by consumers so that it influences consumer perceptions in generating buying interest. The majority of research respondents indicated that they felt review information in the form of products, services and shipping offered by The Special Treats stores and products that consumers wanted to know about could be adopted easily and could be found easily by utilizing social media in searching for online reviews so as to generate curiosity and interest in buying The Special Treats products.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on hypothesis in this study, it can be concluded that the results are in partial mediation, it involves a mediator variable, both directly and indirectly the independent variable will affect the dependent variable.

The hypothesis of Perceived Information Usefulness, Needs of Information has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention (H2, H3, H4). Then followed by Quality of e-WOM and Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) which have a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention (H4, H5). Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) has a positive and significant influence in mediating Needs of Information and Purchase Intention and Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) has a positive and significant influence mediating Perceived Information Usefulness and Purchase Intention (H9, H10). However, in this study there are three hypotheses that have positive but not significant results, namely Quality of e-WOM on Social Media Usage (e-WOM adoption), Perceived Information

Usefulness on Purchase Intention, and Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) which mediates Quality of e-WOM and Purchase Intention (H1, H6 and H8). And finally, one negative and insignificant hypothesis, the Needs of Information on Purchase Intention.

From the research that has been examined and the conclusions that have been obtained, the researcher can provide some suggestions for those who will use the results of this research in the future to deepen research related to Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) and Purchase Intention. Based on the results regarding the R-Square value obtained, the mediating variable with a value of 0.715 or 71.5%. This value still has a few percent which affects the Social Media Usage (e-WOM Adoption) variable. For future researchers, it is necessary to re-examine this research model and involve other variables that have not been studied in this study, such as Trust, Source of Expertise, Homophily and others. In addition, the researcher suggests conducting broader research research, where this research can be carried out with different research locations because this research is dominated by big cities in Indonesia such as Jakarta and Bandung which have different characteristics based on needs and habits in online shopping and the ease of accessing the internet. Future researchers can re-conduct this research using the same variables but with different research objects, such as doing environmental-friendly buying intentions online.

For The Special Treats should pay attention to the importance of the quality of information on online reviews that are owned and shaped in an interesting way and can explain information well to their consumers. The special treats can provide more information about online reviews such as multiplying and placing these online reviews in an album on social media that can be seen publicly and can provide also collect online reviews that can represent reliable and informative information by inviting food bloggers or reviewers who can convey in detail the impressions of the product's message. Furthermore, The Special Treats can be more active on social media to update long-term and short-term information about the products being sold, such as adding funfacts about their products to add insight into using social media and make it easier for consumers to adopt information to increase consumer purchase intention.

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